

Impact of Insecurity on Quality of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria: A Case study of Plateau State Tertiary Institutions

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Abstract

Plateau State, Nigeria has continued to witness protracted violent conflicts in the past three decades that have adversely affected various sectors of the state, including the educational sector. The paper investigates impact of insecurity on quality of tertiary education in Nigeria: A Case study of Plateau State Tertiary institutions. It adopted the Democratic Peace Theory as the theoretical framework to guide the paper. It utilised both secondary and primary data, using qualitative approach. The primary data administered 12 In-depth and 4 Key Informant Interviews using purposive sampling techniques. Content analysis was used to analyze the data. The paper found out that insecurity in the study area gave way to loss of manpower in educational institutions, poor quality of education, destruction of infrastructural facilities, closure of educational institutions, internal displacement of staff and students, reduction of private investment in education. It further submitted that current efforts to mitigate the problems have not yielded enough positive results. The paper, therefore, recommended that the government both at the federal and the state levels should address all the pending issues fuelling insecurities in the state and ensure that the institution is secured and safe enough for teaching and learning. The governments should invest in higher institutions' securities across the state. Since the military approach seems failing, the paper further recommended the adoption of non-kinetic approaches to support the current efforts deployed to combat the menace of insecurity in the University of Jos. Finally, the paper emphasised that the University should intensify awareness programmes for the university community to always observe basic security measures as early warning tactics to mitigate unforeseen attacks; and that the university should invest in Online Distance Learning (ODL) systems to allow the students access virtual teaching experience as alternative learning process.

Keywords: Impact, Insecurity, Tertiary institution.

Introduction

The quality of education, wherever it may be found, is largely determined by the peace and security that permeate the learning environment. Okoli and Okpaleke (2014) noted that education is intended to help people develop their skills and abilities so they can reach their full potential and lead productive, fulfilling lives. In preliterate societies, education was primarily focused on hunting, cooking, following the stars, and obeying the gods. Education is an essential investment for human and economic development.

The government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, according to Nzeh (2015), realized the importance of education and declared in its 1999 Constitution that every Nigerian child has the right to an education, regardless of gender, tribe, religion, or race. It makes sense to state that the high standards of education outlined in the Federal Republic of Nigeria's constitution would be realized in a calm and supportive school environment. Ndoma-Egba (2014) asserts that the noble goals of education can never be achieved in a vacuum. Both teachers and students are likely to be discouraged if there is a sense of insecurity in and around the school, which could impair the students' academic performance. A lack of peace can result in widespread devastation, extreme insecurity, intimidation, and fear, which can close schools and halt instruction for the duration of the school day. Nigerian Institutions that have faced insecurity have experienced many setbacks in terms of academic growth and infrastructural destruction (Nwosu, 2016).

In Nigeria, however, there has been an unprecedented level of insecurity, threatening national security and prompting a significant portion of the national budget to be allocated to security (Achumba, 2013). The alarming level of insecurity in Nigeria has increased the rate of crime and terrorist attacks in various parts of the country, leaving unpalatable

consequences for the country's economy and business growth (Ali, 2013). Agbo (2023) notes that tertiary institutions have not been spared from the negative impact of insecurity. For example, Nigeria has seen a rise in insecurity in recent years, with incidents of kidnapping, armed robbery, violence between communities, terrorism, and other crimes. This has left the educational sector, particularly tertiary institutions, vulnerable to insecurity, with students and staff members at risk of being abducted, attacked, or killed (Agbo, 2023).

Moreso, Umar (2022) noted that the alarming level of insecurity in Nigeria has resulted in an increase in crime and terrorist attacks throughout the country, which has had a negative impact on the country's economy, business, and expansion of education. The Nigerian people now literally sleep with their eyes open, emasculated by the fear of these terror groups and the suffering and destruction they are capable of causing (Agbo, 2023).

In the Plateau State, the stability and operation of higher education institutions are severely hampered by various forms of insecurity. The state is currently mired in an unprecedented level of growing insecurity. These days, it is easier for jihadists, bandits, Fulani herdsmen, kidnappers, and other criminals to waste a human life than an animal (Okoli, 2014). In Plateau State, tertiary institutions are becoming more susceptible to the destabilizing consequences of insecurity. These include risks to the health and safety of instructors and students, interruptions to the regular course of study, difficulties in keeping up campus facilities, and a decline in the legitimacy and trust of the institution (William 2008). Academic calendar delays and extended study periods have resulted from the frequent closures and disruptions caused by insecurity. Students and staff members experience psychological trauma as well, which negatively impacts their mental health and general well being (Nzeh, 2015)

Furthermore, because parents and guardians would be reluctant to send their children to institutions that are prone to insecurity, insecurity could harm the institution's reputation and lower enrollment rates. (Hassan 2023) It might also result in the exodus of highly qualified academics in search of safer workplaces. The security situation in Nigeria seems to be insurmountable, according to Achumba, Ighomereho, and Akpor-Robaro (2013), and many have claimed that the government at all levels has not done enough by not addressing the issue head-on and taking decisive action. Some, however, contend that the circumstances have a political undertone or inclination intended to further the goals of certain political gods who are angry and unsatisfied with the political manifestations in the nation (Ajodo, 2012)). The University of Jos presented a classic case of frequent attacks on tertiary institutions in the country. Using the University as a case study, this paper hope to provide scientific answers to the following questions; how is the spate of insecurity impacting on the quality of education in the university; what are the coping mechanisms of the university authorities and how can the incessant attacks be mitigated to enhance the overall performance and quality of education in the institution?

Conceptual Clarification

Insecurity: The concept of insecurity is a derivative of the term 'security', which literarily means to be safe from hunger, fear, molestation, attacks and any other forms of threats to life or personal safety of a human person. Hence, any situation that can cause fear, attacks or bodily harm to an individual or group of persons can be referred to as insecurity. To Ajodo-Adebanjoko (2014), insecurity is a state of fear or anything that has the potential to cause fear, harm, injury, or destruction to a person, a group, or a country. Ali (2013) claims that since Nigeria returned to democratic rule in 1999, there has been a rise in terrorism-related incidents, which has added to the country's growing sense of unease. People's perception of their level of safety from fear, economic, political, social, cultural, and psychological is known as security. People's relative perception of the existence of social, political, cultural, psychological, and economic fear is known as insecurity. Economic insecurity is the most prevalent type of insecurity among them all and the one that makes other types of insecurity more apparent. Other types of insecurity emerged as a result of economic insecurity. There are several meanings associated with the term insecurity, including: lack of protection, danger, hazard, uncertainty, and absence of safety. Beland (2005) cited in Ewetan and Urhie (2014), states that insecurity is a condition of fear or anxiety brought on by a lack of security.

Tertiary Institution

This is a widely used concept that has attracted universal appeal. International Standard Classification of Education has defined the concept as post-compulsory education system and later as third level of education, which was used to describe all types of education that offer specific courses for adult learning. It later described it as that level of education that 'builds on secondary education, providing learning activities in a specialised field of education' (UNESCO, 2012:46) The uniqueness of tertiary education revolves on the fact that it combines both academic and professional skills at various levels.

Quality Education

This is a major concern of the performance index of major educational institutions worldwide. For Arnold and Bassett, (2021), tertiary institution must exhibit certain values to be rated to have upheld the required quality of education. They suggested that a tertiary education system should steer diverse institutions to encourage equity, efficiency and resilience with clear educational and qualification pathways for learners (Arnold and Bassett, 2021). In Nigeria, and within the purview of this paper, quality education presupposes that for the attainment of effective education system, all the

relevant stakeholders especially policy makers should endeavor to provide the necessary facilities and ensure the conducive leaning environment for all adults.

Methodology

The paper utilised both primary and secondary data collection. The primary data were qualitative in nature and obtained from 12 In-depth Interviews and 4 Key Informant Interviews. These were carried out using purposive sampling techniques. A question guide was designed by the researchers and was used to gather or administer interviews on the respondents. The respondents were selected from different section of the University of Jos and representatives from government cycles. These included student leaders, university staff, and government officials. The data gathered were analysed using content analysis. The secondary data were sourced from books, government papers, journal articles: print and online, conference proceedings, and materials related to the subject matter.

The Democratic Peace Theory is used in this study to explain Nigeria's security issues. This theory, put forth by Michael Doyle in 1998, holds that a security policy's long-term goal must be the spread of liberalism and that security primarily rests on assisting liberal institutions in carrying out their duties in an honorable manner (Doyle, 1998). Thus, promoting democracy, universal respect for human rights, and the growth of civil society are the paths that lead to peace. However, such a conclusion is primarily predicated on a stable and strong correlation between a state's democratic nature and its propensity for peace. Therefore, liberal states are assumed to refrain from waging war on other liberal states by the democratic peace theory.

Michael Doyle initially presented this theory in a keynote paper published in the *Journal of Philosophy and Public Affairs* (Doyle, 1998). Doyle therefore contended that liberal behavior toward liberal societies differed from liberal behavior toward non-liberal societies. The democratic peace theory makes clear recommendations from a security perspective.

Insecurity and Quality of Education

As a fundamental idea, insecurity is frequently linked to circumstances where values are threatened, particularly the survival of people, groups, or objects in the near future. As the name suggests, insecurity therefore refers to the incapacity to pursue desired political and socioeconomic conditions that are supportive of democracy. A state of no safety, confidence, and the pervasiveness of danger, fear, and doubts is known as insecurity. It might also refer to a situation, in which one is unsafe, poorly guarded, or both, and where instability predominates as opposed to desired stability. Fear or anxiety resulting from a real or perceived lack of protection is referred to as insecurity. It alludes to insufficient or nonexistent safety from harm.

The most obvious type of insecurity is physical insecurity, which is reflected in this definition. Physical insecurity also contributes to many other types of insecurity, including social and economic security. According to William (2008), feeling uncertain, erratic, unsteady, nervous, or lacking in confidence are all examples of insecurity. This may stem from one's upbringing, uncomfortable situations, maltreatment, or personal fears. The term insecurity describes a condition in which one is constantly confronted with threats, dangers, molestation, intimidation, harassment, etc. One way to conceptualize insecurity is as threats to the state, which is why there has often been a race to acquire weapons, including nuclear weapons, in order to defend the state.

The absence of safety and peace is what is commonly referred to as insecurity, which is problematic because security is unquestionably the cornerstone required for the advancement of society, politics, and education. Any nation's citizens are under grave danger from insecurity, which also acts as a Canker-worm that eats away at the foundation of any nation. Nwakpa (2015) examined the effect of insecurity on quality tertiary education in Nigeria. The study was conducted in Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. The study found out that examination fever, lack of self-confidence, frustration and not being admitted into a course of preference/choice are the source of insecurity that affects the quality of tertiary education in Nigeria. The study recommends that government should fund education properly and effectively monitor the activities of private operators in the education sector. There is need for proper and regular counseling of students and their parents/guardians to eschew fraud in education. causes, of insecurity in tertiary educational institutions, and strategies to be employed. Finally, the study made some recommendations to include, full implementation of the suggested strategies.

Agazuma and Mochi (2021) conducted a research on emerging insecurity challenges and its impact on quality tertiary education in Nigeria. The study was done in Delta State University, Abraka and Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted and a total of 682 respondents were selected for the study using the random and proportionate-stratified sampling method. A correlation index of 0.81 was obtained to determine the reliability of the instrument that is, the questionnaire which was self-designed. Responses to the questions raised were analyzed using the mean statistics and the hypotheses were tested using the chi square statistics of 0.05 level of significance. The study discovered that insecurity has drastically and to a large extent affected effective and efficient running of the school system in Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma and Delta States University, Abraka. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that: Government and school administrators should shun corruption, oppression, and highhandedness

and take unbiased stand in handling matters affecting the students. Also recommended was that the university system must at all-time stick to rules of engagement. All acts capable of breeding crisis must be discouraged.

Abubakar, Abdulkadir and Shuaibu (2023) investigated the security challenges and control measure in six (6) college of education libraries in North-East, Nigeria. Survey research design was employed. Questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. Frequency and percentages were the statistical tools used for data analysis. The population and sample consisted of 20 staff (librarians, library officers and library assistants) from the six colleges used for the study. Results from the study revealed absence of the use of information communication technology (ICT) to safeguard library collection as a results of poor power supply; that both print and electronic materials are targets of crime in libraries, with non-return of library materials, theft and mutilation constituting security challenges in these libraries. It was also discovered that various methods were adopted for stealing and mutilation of library materials such as ripping off book page(s), removing the book jackets, and hiding of books under their clothes and in pockets. It was recommended that photocopy service should be provided to enable the library users to photocopy books that are few in the library; that managements should provide multiple copies of materials to meet the information needs of their users.

Hassan (2023) examined the effect of insecurity on the education system in Kaduna state. A total of 1000 made up of 500 each of male and female students responded to a self-structured validated questionnaire designed for the study. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Means and standard deviations were calculated to answer the research questions and independent samples t-tests were used for testing the hypotheses. Major findings revealed that insecurity of school environment significantly affects the academic performance of secondary school students while students' gangsterism, smoking of Indian hemp, abusing other hard drugs, cult and related violent activities were some of the factors that constituted insecurity of the school environment which eventually cause boys to leave school and join trading while leading girls to drop out and settle for marriage. Based on the findings, it was recommended that owners of schools and other stakeholders in education should take bold steps to fence and protect school environments from intruders to ensure safety of the students.

Is'haq, Musa and Abdulhafiz (2019) worked on education and Insecurity in Nigeria. This study examined the relationship between state of education and insecurity in Nigeria. The survey research design was adopted for the study. One hundred and fifteen (115) respondents were randomly selected across the six geo-political zones in the country. The selection was done through the distribution of the research instrument, questionnaire, titled "Education and Insecurity Assessment Scale (EIAS)". The instrument was designed by the researchers, and constructed in a 4-point likert scale format. Data obtained for the study were analysed using the descriptive statistics of frequency counts, mean (\bar{x}) and simple percentage. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the formulated hypotheses. The study revealed inadequate education as the root cause of insecurity and; significant relationship between inefficacious education and insecurity associated with penury, unemployment, corruption, kidnapping and insurgency in Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, accordance of education priority in the national budget, and creation of effective database in Nigeria among others are recommended.

Insecurity and its impact on Jos University

The main goal of Nigeria's post-secondary educational institutions is to provide students with a solid and high-quality education that will enable them succeed in any field or discipline of their choice (Iyoha et al., 2010 cited in Agazuma and Mochi, 2021). Due to its extensive effects and direct consequences on education, the economy, and society at large, Nigeria's high level of insecurity has emerged as a social issue and a multifaceted problem that demands attention. The most concerning aspect of modern Nigeria is the emergence of new insecurity challenges, which have become so severe as to nearly completely cripple the country's various sectors, particularly the education sector.

It has been noted that the goals of higher education in Nigeria can only be achieved in settings that are safe, tranquil, and supportive of instruction, learning, and the execution of research projects. The curriculum is implemented by the academic staff. Professional teachers are hired by every educational system to provide instruction as well as other educational services. Teachers are essential to any educational setting. Teachers are thought of as the institution's engine room. Teachers in Nigeria's public schools face a variety of difficulties (Ogunode, Okwelogu, and Ahaotu, 2021).

According to Agazuma and Mochi (2021), an environment marked by violence and insecurity makes it impossible to provide high-quality education. A quality education prepares students to be engaged and productive members of society and is sound both pedagogically and development. Even though there has been a lot of public discussion about the issue of insecurity over the years, it seems that interest in finding a solution is dwindling, and even when it is, the potential socioeconomic and political ramifications are rarely or never considered. As a result, any country with low levels of education will inevitably have low states. For this reason, education has remained a key driver of national development. Nwosu (2016) noted that competent and seasoned instructors would rather be moved to a different school where their safety is guaranteed. Education resources are always destroyed during times of crisis, and given the high risks involved, the nations that have historically supported such initiatives will be hesitant to do so in conflict zones. The person who ends up on the receiving end is the leaner. In Nigeria as in most other parts of the world, educational institutions and higher learning

centers are frequently singled out during times of crisis. According to UNESCO (2010), in accordance with this submission, students will not be able to concentrate fully on their studies because they will not be at ease. The threat will always make them fearful in schools. Research indicates that there is a rise in deviant behavioral traits across the nation, and in the higher education system in particular. Due to the ongoing instability in the Nigerian state, the majority of Nigeria's post-secondary educational institutions are having a lot of difficulty realizing these educational objectives. Effective given the current state of insecurity in the nation. This all boils down to the idea that an organization, society, or system is threatened by insecurity.

According to Omorogbe (2016), the nation's insecurity has the potential to significantly lower the performance, goals, and objectives of the educational system and, if left unchecked, could completely destroy the education sector. For this reason, this study will promote peace and the absence of conflict and insecurity in Nigerian education system. These institutions are continuously on fire due to the demonic activities of cult members. Insecurity breeds fear, anxiety, uncertainty, death, and disruption of academic activities and programs, among other negative emotions. Campus insecurity has a detrimental impact on the educational process. It sometimes causes disruptions to the academic calendar and instills fear and feelings of insecurity in tertiary institution staff and students. Because no nation can grow above the capabilities of its tertiary institutions, the disruption of learning on campus poses a threat to national development. Ohiare-Udebu and Ogunode, Rauf (2021) note that the closing of schools, which has impacted the country's higher education system's academic calendar, is the most concerning aspect of the insecurity.

Due to university closures and the discontinuation of numerous academic programs, numerous faculties and departments are unable to graduate their students. A riot over a fee bike and a lack of facilities occurred in November of 2015. The students union requested that the management discontinue the annual ICT and development levies because, in their words, the students were not using the facilities. 2016 saw the University of Jos' Naraguta complex library burned down. This was another instance of property damage, specifically to the building, its amenities, its books, and the processed results of the students' exam scripts. According to Ogunode and Musa (2020), academic staff members are being forced to relocate across the nation as a result of the ongoing insurgency and violence plaguing higher education institutions, as well as the ongoing murders of academic staff members by bandits and rebels. Many lecturers are leaving states with high security risk to states where the security risk is lower. This submission is confirmed by Jimada, who observed that many schools have closed down due Boko Haram activities and lack of talented lecturers. Teachers have abandoned their schools for other schools in another peaceful states leading to brain drain in such regions. More than 800 school buildings have been affected in the North leading to some students having their classes under trees and canopies.

In support of the above view, as observed by an informant interviewed:

The ongoing attacks on lecturers in and around higher education institutions in Nigeria and especially here in Jos are causing a shortage of qualified teachers. Many academic staff and professors have left the high-risk, prone areas because of the risk of insecurity. Many academics are being forced to move to more peaceful areas of the country due to the insecurity in Plateau State.

A professor interviewed asserted that: Numerous research projects at universities have been suspended or terminated, particularly at universities in Northern Nigeria, such as Jos, where insecurity concerns have forced university closures. There is no way for a lecturer to conduct research in an unsafe setting. The lecturers need to feel comfortable, and the environment needs to be secure, for meaningful research to occur.

One of the students at the University of Jos added that: Apart from disruptions of classes and academic calendar, it also creates fears among us students and even on the staff members too. Insecurity can lead to a decrease in enrolment as students may be hesitant to attend a school located in an area that they perceive as unsafe. I mean no reasonable parents will send his child to a hostile environment.

Another informant observed that: Insecurity in this state has actually affected our academic activities. It has indeed affected the academic activities of a tertiary institution as students and staff may be afraid to come to the campus for fear of their safety. This can lead to a decrease in academic performance and research activities. It has also led to a decrease in staff retention as some may be unwilling to work in an environment that they perceive as unsafe. At least I know some of our staff members who left due to the insecurity that started since 2001.

From the above views expressed by the respondents, it is clear that the effects of insecurity on higher education institutions go beyond direct threats to safety but have wider ramifications for reputation, academic integrity, and the quality of the educational process. It takes a careful examination of the many ways that insecurity manifested itself as well as the various environments in which tertiary institutions function to fully comprehend the complexities of how these institutions are impacted. According to Agazuma and Mochi (2021), there are several ways that insecurity affects education. First, it has a significant negative impact on the effective and efficient operation of the school system. Secondly, students and staff lose faith in the government's ability to protect them. Third, students' academic work and activities are also negatively impacted. Lastly, some staff members and students find it difficult to attend school or even to stay in school because of fear of lack of protection and safety.

Wilson (2019) noted that ensuring efficient student administration and enrollment is one of the responsibilities of school administration; however, the nation's insecurity is deterring parents and kids from sending their kids to school out of fear that they will be kidnapped or killed by insurgents. Many parents have made the decision to keep their kids at home rather than risk having them killed or abducted from schools where there is no guarantee of safety. Parents in Nigeria are considering removing their children from school due to security threats. Wilson (2019) observes that Nigerian education is suffering greatly as a result of the recent wave of kidnappings. In the midst of a pandemic, when some parents have pulled their kids out of school, or have chosen not to send their kids back to school, the unrest and dangers to educational infrastructure will only make an already challenging situation worse. Students' internal displacement in Nigeria is a result of insecurity, particularly in the country's north. The state of unrest has forced many students to leave their schools. Students' administration in educational institutions across the nation is being impacted by insecurity. When a terrorist organization targets a community, schools are frequently among their first targets. Increased numbers of internally displaced people, political, social, and economic upheavals, and sluggish economic growth are some of the effects of insecurity. All of the aforementioned have a detrimental effect on the people who live in such unsafe places.

Conclusion

This paper investigated the impact of insecurity on quality of tertiary education in Plateau State, Nigeria. It is only when tertiary institutions' surroundings are tranquil, safe, and supportive of instruction, learning, and the execution of research projects can the goals of higher education in Nigeria be achieved. A sustainable development of higher education in Nigeria cannot be guaranteed by students, non-academic staff, or academic staff in light of the recent attacks in Plateau State, which have had a significant impact on tertiary institutions. The paper concluded that insecurity in Plateau State gave rise to disruptions in academic programs, particularly in the area of research, loss of manpower in educational institutions, poor quality of education, destruction of infrastructural facilities, closure educational institution, internal displacement of staff and students, reduction of private investment in education.

Recommendations

In view of the above, this paper makes the following recommendations:

1. Government both at state and federal levels should address all issues fuelling insecurities in the state and ensure higher institutions are secured and safe for teaching and learning.
2. The governments should invest in higher institutions' securities across the state. Since the military approach appears to be failing, political leaders should have the political will to fight the insecurity in the state through the use of best strategies, which must include the adoption of non-kinetic approach such as the use of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) processes and other strategic peace-building initiatives.
3. Since insecurity persists in Plateau State, this paper advocates the adoption of virtual teaching options to mitigate the exposure of students to frequent attacks on educational facilities and by extension, the school authorities should endeavor to invest more on Online Distance Learning (ODL) infrastructure.
4. Finally, there is the need for the school authorities to step up awareness programmes for students, staff and immediate environment where the school is situated to observe basic security measures such early warning systems for proactively responding and mitigating unforeseen attacks.

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